

ECONOMIC CONSIDERATIONS IN FOLK'S ORAL CREATION

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Annotation: In this article, one of the sources of Uzbek oral folk art, Alpomish epic, provides detailed information about economic relations based on Islamic teachings, the level of development of the division of labor, the commodity-money and financial system.

Keywords: epic, folk, Uzbek, thought, song, economy, islam, teaching, history, attitude.

It is important in the development of the economic thinking of the Uzbek people one of the sources is examples of folk art. This examples include epics, folk proverbs and songs. One of the unique monuments of our historical heritage is the Alpomish saga. The evidence confirms that this saga was formed more than a thousand years ago. That is why the thousandth anniversary of the Alpomish was widely celebrated in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2000.[1]

In addition to the artistic value of the work, economic views are also important. The composition of economic relations in the Alpomish saga can be grouped as follows:

1. Economic relations based on Islamic teachings. This the relationship is based on issues related to zakat and juzya payments. That is, the dispute between Alpomish's father Boybori and his brother Boysaribi regarding payment of zakat.[2]

2. The level of development of the division of labor. From the epic It seems that by that time, the livestock industry of Kungirov clan is an indicator of specialization.[3]

3. Commodity-money and financial system relations. In the saga As mentioned, nature in commodity-monetary relations of bells and whistles the priority of payments is shown and in the Kalmyk state, regulation of income and expenses is carried out through the post of mukhdar.[4]

The seal relies on taxes and fees collected by the elders to keep records of income and expenses. 500 eldership positions have been introduced in this country.

Their salary is a part of collected taxes. A salary of 500 monetary units was assigned to the Sipohis.[5]

Information is provided that the currency used for transactions is minted gold and silver from neighboring countries. On the one hand, the source of taxes

is the land tax, and on the other hand, the fees collected from trade caravans and the domestic market are considered. In general, works of folklore are one of the important sources for explaining the economic relations in the history of the nation. Proverbs of the Uzbek people are also a component of economic beliefs. Therefore, it is important to use examples of folk art to ensure harmony of national economic thinking with universal human values.

References:

1. Razzokov A. Analysis of the economy of developed countries. Educational-methodical manual. T., 2001. – P.26.
2. Yuldashev K. and Muftaydinov K. From the history of economic doctrines (On the example of Eastern economic thinking). T., 2000. – P.19.
3. Sagdullaev A. History of Uzbekistan: development of the state and society. T., Academy. 2000 – P.56.
- 4 . Петросянц В. С. Политические учения Древний Греции. -М.: “Наука”, 1919. – с.56.
5. Olmasov A., Sharifkhojayev M. Economic theory. Tashkent, 1995. – P.78.